

RIGOUROUS OF PRIME TRIPLE AND QUADRUPLE'S CONJECTURE

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a rigorous proof of the prime triple's Conjecture and quadruple's Conjecture is provided. This proof is mainly based on a very special class of prime numbers; the set of f_n -prime. We show that it is always possible to generate a prime triple and quadruplet. The keys of our proof is Chebotarev-Artin theorem, Mertens formula and Poincare sieve. The results show us as that the density of f_n -prime is $\frac{5}{3}C_{artin} + 2K_\infty - 1$ where

$$K_\infty = \prod_{n=1}^{+\infty} \left(1 - \frac{1}{(p_n - 1)((p_{n+1} - 1)}\right)$$

with p_n is the n th prime. Moreover we obtain the function $R_2(n)$ which counts the number of prime p such that $p - 6, p - 4$ are both prime

$$R_2(n) \sim_{+\infty} \left(2 - \frac{5}{3}C_{artin} - 2K_\infty\right) \frac{n}{\ln n}$$

and the function $R_3(n)$ which counts the generators of prime triple and quadruplet

$$R_3(n) \sim_{+\infty} 4e^{-\gamma} \left(2 - \frac{5}{3}C_{artin} - 2K_\infty\right) C_2 \frac{n}{\ln^2 n}$$

Thus, this results provide a rigorous proof for prime triple's and quadruplet's conjecture which is still considered, to our best knowledge, among the open problems of mathematics.

1 INTRODUCTION

As with twin primes, prime quadruplets generally become scarcer the higher one looks for them with the aid of the computer, yet they also display the same unevenness of distribution: there is only one prime quadruplet between 40000 and 50000, yet there are three between 70000 and 80000. While Euclid proved long ago that there are infinitely many primes, it is still not known whether there are also infinitely many prime quadruplets.

The question is related to the twin prime conjecture: proving the prime quadruplet conjecture would automatically prove the twin prime conjecture as well. However, disproving the prime quadruplet conjecture might not necessarily disprove the twin prime conjecture as well. Hardy and Littlewood stated their conjecture in more general terms as the prime k-tuple conjecture, with the case of the prime quadruplets being for $k=4$. As far as the studies about prime triple, the first known gigantic was found in 2008 by Norman Luhn and François Morain. The primes are $(p, p+2, p+6)$ with $p = 2072644824759^{233333} - 1$. As of August 2018 the largest known prime triplet contains primes with 16737 digits and was found by Peter Kaiser. The primes are $(p, p+4, p+6)$ with $p = 6521953289619^{255555} - 5$. It is conjectured that there are infinitely many such primes. In fact the Hardy-Littlewood prime k-tuple conjecture suggests that the number less than x of each of the forms $(p, p+2, p+6)$ and $(p, p+4, p+6)$. In our paper we are going to give a beautiful proof to the prime triple and quadruple conjecture

2 DEFINITIONS

This part will consist to give the definition of the main concepts used in our paper

Let n be an integer such as above 20 and denote by C_n the set of the old composite integers of the interval $[9, n]$ f_n be the function defined as : $f_n : C_n \mapsto \mathbb{N}^2, m \mapsto (m+4, m+6)$ Denote by P_n denotes the set of prime less than n . Let

$$G_n = \{m+4 \in P_{n+4} : m \in C_n\}$$

and

$$G'_n = \{m+6 \in P_{n+6} : m \in C_n\}$$

An integer m is called to be f_n prime if $f_n(m)$ has at least one component prime The set of f_n -prime of C_n is $G_n \cup G'_n$

2.1 Thot Primes

A Thot prime is the prime $p \geq 11$ such that $p - 4, p - 6$ are both prime

2.2 Prime triple and quadruple generator

A prime is said to be prime triple and quadruple if p is Thot prime such that $p - 2$ is prime .

2.3 Predactor Sequence

We define a predactor sequence as

$$\Delta_n^1 = \prod_{3 \leq p \leq \sqrt{n}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p(p-1)}\right) + \prod_{3 \leq p < q \leq \sqrt{n}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{(q-1)(p-1)}\right) - \prod_{3 \leq p \leq \sqrt{n}} \frac{p-2}{p-1} - 1$$

and

$$\Delta_n^2 = 3 \prod_{3 \leq p \leq \sqrt{n}} \frac{p-2}{p-1} - \prod_{3 \leq p \leq \sqrt{n}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p(p-1)}\right)$$

3 LEMMAS

3.1 LEMMA 1

$\forall n \geq 20, P_{n+6} \setminus G_n \cup G'_n \neq \emptyset$

3.2 LEMMA 2

$\forall n \geq 9$ the set of Thot primes contains

$$\{p \in P_{n+6} \setminus G_n \cup G'_n : 11 \leq p \leq n + 4\}$$

3.3 USEFULL LEMMA

Let a_1, a_2, \dots, a_r be r numbers Then

$$1 - \sum_{i=1}^r \frac{1}{a_i} + \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq r} \frac{1}{a_i a_j} + \dots + \frac{(-1)^r}{a_1 a_2 \dots a_r} = \prod_{i=1}^r \frac{a_i - 1}{a_i}$$

4 THEOREM

Let n be an integer , $R_3(n)$ the numbers of prime triple and quadruple generators then

$$R_3(n) \sim_{+\infty} 4e^{-\gamma} \left(2 - \frac{5}{3}C_{artin} - 2K_\infty\right) C_2 \frac{n}{\ln^2 n}$$

4.1 Theorem 1

the density of $f_n(C_n)$ - prime numbers is $\frac{5}{3}C_{artin} + 2K_\infty - 1$

4.2 Theorem 2

Let n be an arbitraly large integer

$$card(P_{n+6} \setminus G_n \cup G'_n) \sim_{+\infty} \left(2 - \frac{5}{3}C_{artin} - 2K_\infty\right) \frac{n}{\ln n}$$

4.3 Theorem 3

Let n be an integer and $R_3(n)$ the function which counts the prime triple and quadruple generator then

$$R_3(n) \sim_{+\infty} 4e^{-\gamma} \left(2 - \frac{5}{3}C_{artin} - 2K_\infty\right) C_2 \frac{n}{\ln^2 n}$$

5 Prime triplet conjecture

5.1 PROOF OF USEFULL LEMMA

For the proof of USEFULL LEMMA ,we consider the Polynomial:

$$P(X) = \prod_{i=1}^r \left(X - \frac{1}{a_i}\right)$$

from the coefficient-roots relations we also have :

$$P(X) = X^r + \sum_{k=1}^r \sum_{1 \leq i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_k \leq r} \frac{(-1)^k X^{r-k}}{\prod_{j=1}^k a_{i_j}}$$

For $X = 1$ the result follows

CONCLUSION

In our work we have proved that there are many types of quadruple and triple primes .We have also determined the way to build triple and quadruple prime .For the given n the chance to be prime is $\frac{1}{\ln n}$ and also the chance to be prime triple and quadruple generator is

$$4e^{-\gamma}(2 - \frac{5}{3}C_{artin} - 2K_{\infty})C_2\frac{1}{\ln^2 n}$$

Then the density of prime triple and quadruple less than a given n is

$$\simeq 4e^{-\gamma}(2 - \frac{5}{3}C_{artin} - 2K_{\infty})C_2\frac{n}{\ln^3 n}$$

5.2 PROOF OF THE LEMMA 1

Each $m \in C_n$ has at least one prime divisor $p \leq \sqrt{n}$

Let $r = \max\{i : p_i \leq \sqrt{n}\}$ $C_n = \bigcup_{p \in P_{\sqrt{n}, p \geq 3}} A_{2p}$ with $A_{2p} = \{3p, 4p, 5p, \dots, [\frac{n-p}{2p}]p\}$

$$f_n(C_n) = \bigcup_{p \in P_{\sqrt{n}, p \geq 3}} f_n(A_{2p})$$

Then $f_n(C_n) = \bigcup_{p \in P_{\sqrt{n}, p \geq 3}} \{A_{2p} + 4\} \times \{A_{2p} + 6\}$ Denote by ρ_2 the function which counts the number of f_n -prime in a given set A then by the Poincare sieve we have :

$$\rho_2(f_n(C_n)) = \sum_{k=2}^r (-1)^k \sum_{2 \leq i_2 < i_3 < \dots < i_k \leq r} \rho_2\left(\bigcap_{j=2}^k f_n(A_{2p_{i_j}})\right)$$

Also

$$\forall k \geq 3, \bigcap_{j=1}^k f_n(A_{2p_{i_j}}) = \{(m \prod_{j=2}^k p_{i_j} + 4, m \prod_{j=2}^k p_{i_j} + 6) : 1 \leq m \leq [\frac{n - \prod_{j=2}^k p_{i_j}}{2 \prod_{j=2}^k p_{i_j}}]\}$$

Let $E_{1,m} = \{m \prod_{j=2}^k p_{i_j} + 4\}$ and $E_{2,m} = \{m \prod_{j=2}^k p_{i_j} + 6\}$ Counting the number of f_n - prime in $\bigcap_{j=1}^k f_n(A_{2p_{i_j}})$ consisting on counting the number of prime in $\bigcup_{1 \leq m \leq [\frac{n - \prod_{j=2}^k p_{i_j}}{2 \prod_{j=2}^k p_{i_j}}]} E_{2,m} \cup E_{1,m}$

$$\rho_2\left(\bigcap_{j=2}^k f_n(A_{2p_{i_j}})\right) = \rho_2\left(\bigcup_{1 \leq m \leq [\frac{n - \prod_{j=2}^k p_{i_j}}{2 \prod_{j=2}^k p_{i_j}}]} E_{2,m} \cup E_{1,m}\right)$$

Let ρ be the function which counts the number of prime in a given set then

$$\rho_2\left(\bigcup_{1 \leq m \leq \lfloor \frac{n - \prod_{j=2}^k p_{i_j}}{2 \prod_{j=2}^k p_{i_j}} \rfloor} E_{2,m} \cup E_{1,m}\right) = \rho\left(\left[\bigcup_{1 \leq m \leq \lfloor \frac{n - \prod_{j=2}^k p_{i_j}}{2 \prod_{j=2}^k p_{i_j}} \rfloor} E_{2,m}\right] \cup \left[\bigcup_{1 \leq m \leq \lfloor \frac{n - \prod_{j=2}^k p_{i_j}}{2 \prod_{j=2}^k p_{i_j}} \rfloor} E_{1,m}\right]\right)$$

Then

$$\rho\left(\left[\bigcup_{1 \leq m \leq \lfloor \frac{n - \prod_{j=2}^k p_{i_j}}{2 \prod_{j=2}^k p_{i_j}} \rfloor} E_{2,m}\right] \cup \left[\bigcup_{1 \leq m \leq \lfloor \frac{n - \prod_{j=2}^k p_{i_j}}{2 \prod_{j=2}^k p_{i_j}} \rfloor} E_{1,m}\right]\right) = \rho(A_k) + \rho(B_k) - \rho(A_k \cap B_k)$$

where $A_k = \left[\bigcup_{1 \leq m \leq \lfloor \frac{n - \prod_{j=2}^k p_{i_j}}{2 \prod_{j=2}^k p_{i_j}} \rfloor} E_{2,m}\right]$, $B_k = \left[\bigcup_{1 \leq m \leq \lfloor \frac{n - \prod_{j=2}^k p_{i_j}}{2 \prod_{j=2}^k p_{i_j}} \rfloor} E_{1,m}\right]$ Counting the number of prime in A_k , B_k corresponding to count the number of prime in arithmetic progression of reason $2 \prod_{j=2}^k p_{i_j}$ and first term $\prod_{j=2}^k p_{i_j} + 6$ respectively $\prod_{j=2}^k p_{i_j} + 4$ By Chebotarev-Artin theorem we have

$$\rho(A_k) = \frac{\Pi(n+6)}{\prod_{j=2}^k (p_{i_j} - 1), p_{i_j} \nmid 6} + g(n)$$

$$\rho(B_k) = \frac{\Pi(n+4)}{\prod_{j=2}^k (p_{i_j} - 1)} + g(n)$$

And

$$\rho_2(f_n(A_{2p_i})) = \frac{\Pi(n+4)}{\phi(2p_i)} + \frac{\Pi(n+6)}{\phi(2p_i)} - \psi_{p_i+4} - \psi_{p_i+6} - \rho(A_2 \cap B_2) + g(n), \forall i \geq 2$$

. Let $m = \overline{4, 6}$ According to the fact that $\psi_{p_i+m} = 1$ if $p_i + m$ is prime and 0 if not

$$\rho_2(f_n(C_n)) = g(n) - \sum_{i=2}^r [\psi_{p_i+4} + \psi_{p_i+6}] + \beta(n) - \omega(n)$$

where

$$\beta(n) = \sum_{k=2}^r (-1)^k \sum_{2 \leq i_2 < i_3 \dots < i_k \leq r} \left[\frac{\Pi(n+4)}{\prod_{j=2}^k (p_{i_j} - 1)} + \frac{\Pi(n+6)}{\prod_{j=2}^k (p_{i_j} - 1), p_{i_j} \nmid 6} \right]$$

and

$$\omega(n) = \sum_{k=2}^r (-1)^k \sum_{2 \leq i_2 < i_3 \dots < i_k \leq r} [\rho(A_k \cap B_k)]$$

As $A_k \cap B_k = \bigcup_{1 \leq m \leq \lfloor \frac{n - \prod_{j=2}^k p_{i_j}}{2 \prod_{j=2}^k p_{i_j}} \rfloor} [E_{2,m} \cap E_{1,m}]$ Moreover using the fact that

$E_{2,m} \cap E_{1,m} = f_n(X_{1,m})$ where $X_{1,m} = \{m \prod_{j \geq s, s \geq 2}^k p_{i_j} p_{i_s}\}$ For evaluating the prime in $E_{2,m} \cap E_{1,m}$ we are going to use the Chebotarev-Artin theorem Then

$$\rho(A_k \cap B_k) = \frac{\Pi(n+4)}{\phi(\prod_{j \geq s, s \geq 2}^k p_{i_j} p_{i_s})} + \frac{\Pi(n+6)}{\phi(\prod_{j \geq s, s \geq 2}^k p_{i_j} p_{i_s})} + g(n)$$

Where g is the error so

$$\omega(n) = \sum_{k=2}^r (-1)^k \sum_{2 \leq i_2 < i_3 < \dots < i_k \leq r} \left[\frac{\Pi(n+4)}{\phi(\prod_{j \geq s, s \geq 2}^k p_{i_j} p_{i_s})} + \frac{\Pi(n+6)}{\phi(\prod_{j \geq s, s \geq 2}^k p_{i_j} p_{i_s})} \right] + g(n)$$

then

$$\omega(n) = \mu(n) + \alpha(n) + g(n)$$

By the usefull lemma we have :

$$\mu(n) = \Pi(n+4) \left[1 - \prod_{i=2}^r \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i(p_i-1)} \right) \right] + \Pi(n+6) \left[1 - \prod_{i=3}^r \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i(p_i-1)} \right) \right]$$

$$\alpha(n) = \Pi(n+4) \left[1 - \prod_{j \geq s+1, s \geq 2}^r \left(1 - \frac{1}{(p_j-1)(p_s-1)} \right) \right] + \Pi(n+6) \left[1 - \prod_{j \geq s+1, s \geq 2}^r \left(1 - \frac{1}{(p_j-1)(p_s-1)} \right) \right]$$

and

$$\beta(n) = \Pi(n+4) \left[1 - \prod_{i=2}^r \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i-1} \right) \right] + \Pi(n+6) \left[1 - \prod_{i=3}^r \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i-1} \right) \right]$$

$$\beta(n) = [\Pi(n+4) + \Pi(n+6)] \left[1 - \prod_{3 \leq p \leq \sqrt{n}} \frac{p-2}{p-1} \right] + \frac{\Pi(n+4)}{2} \prod_{3 \leq p \leq \sqrt{n}} \frac{p-2}{p-1}$$

$$\omega(n) = [\Pi(n+4) + \Pi(n+6)] \left[2 - \prod_{3 \leq p \leq \sqrt{n}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p(p-1)} \right) - \prod_{3 \leq p < q \leq \sqrt{n}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{(q-1)(p-1)} \right) \right] + z_n$$

$$\text{where } z_n = \frac{\Pi(n+4)}{6} \prod_{3 \leq p \leq \sqrt{n}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p(p-1)} \right)$$

Let

$$\Pi_2(\sqrt{n}) = \text{card}(p \in P_{\sqrt{n}} : p+4 \in P)$$

and

$$\Pi_3(\sqrt{n}) = \text{card}(p \in P_{\sqrt{n}} : p+6 \in P)$$

then

$$\rho_2(f_n(C_n)) = \Delta_n^1 [\Pi(n+4) + \Pi(n+6)] + \Delta_n^2 \frac{\Pi(n+4)}{6} - \Pi_3(\sqrt{n}) - \Pi_2(\sqrt{n}) + g(n)$$

5.3 PROOF OF LEMMA 2

Let $p \in P_{n+6} \setminus G_n \cup G'_n$ such that $11 \leq p \leq n+4$ then $p-4, p-6$ are both prime. Suppose that $p-4$ is not prime as $p-4 \geq 6$ and odd integer then $p-4 \in C_n$ then $f_n(p-4) = (p, p+2)$ so $p \in G_n$ what is impossible

6 STUDY OF PREDACTOR SEQUENCE

This part will consist on evaluating the Predactor sequence

Let

$$C_{artin}(n) = \prod_{2 \leq p \leq \sqrt{n}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p(p-1)}\right)$$

and

$$C_2(n) = \prod_{3 \leq p \leq \sqrt{n}} \frac{p(p-2)}{(p-1)^2}$$

$$K_n = \prod_{2 \leq p < q \leq \sqrt{n}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{(q-1)(p-1)}\right)$$

According to the Mertens formula we have $\prod_{2 \leq p \leq n} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p}\right) = \frac{e^{-\gamma}}{\ln n} (1 + \mathcal{O}(\frac{1}{\ln n}))$ then $\prod_{3 \leq p \leq \sqrt{n}} \frac{p-2}{p-1} = 2 \prod_{2 \leq p \leq \sqrt{n}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p}\right) C_2(n)$ Then

$$\prod_{3 \leq p \leq \sqrt{n}} \frac{p-2}{p-1} = \frac{4e^{-\gamma} C_2(n)}{\ln n} (1 + \mathcal{O}(\frac{1}{\ln n}))$$

Then $\Delta_n^1 = 2C_{artin}(n) + 2K_n - \frac{4e^{-\gamma} C_2(n)}{\ln n} (1 + \mathcal{O}(\frac{1}{\ln n})) - 1$ Then

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \Delta_n^1 = 2C_{artin} + 2K_\infty - 1$$

and

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \Delta_n^2 = -2C_{artin}$$

6.1 PROOF OF THEOREM 1

Let define $R_1(n)$ as

$$R_1(n) = \frac{\text{card}(G_n \cup G'_n)}{\Pi(n+6)}$$

$$R_1(n) = \frac{\Delta_n^1[\Pi(n+4) + \Pi(n+6)] + \Delta_n^2 \frac{\Pi(n+4)}{6} - \Pi_3(\sqrt{n}) - \Pi_2(\sqrt{n}) + g(n)}{\Pi(n+6)}$$

As $\Pi(n+6) = \Pi(n+4) + \psi(n+5) + \psi(n+6)$ then

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} R_1(n) = \frac{5}{3} C_{artin} + 2K_\infty - 1$$

6.2 PROOF OF THEOREM 2

Let $R_2 = \lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{\text{card}(P_{n+6} \setminus G_n \cup G'_n)}{\Pi(n+6)}$ Then

$$R_2 = 1 - \lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} R_1(n)$$

By using the THEOREM 1 we have :

$$R_2 = 2 - \frac{5}{3}C_{artin} - 2K_\infty$$

As $\Pi(n+6) \sim_{+\infty} \frac{n}{\ln n}$ the result follows.

6.3 PROOF OF THEOREM 3

Let define the function $h_n : C_n \mapsto \mathbb{N}, m \mapsto m+2$ Let $\mathbb{T}_n = \{m+2 \in \mathbb{P} : m \in C_n\}$ then $h_n(C_n) = \bigcup_{p \in P_{\sqrt{n}}, p \geq 3} A_{2p+2}$ Let $\mathbb{F}_n = P_{n+6} \setminus G_n \cup G'_n$ and $\mathbb{M}_n = \mathbb{F}_n \setminus \mathbb{T}_n$ Our objective is to prove that $\mathbb{M}_n \neq \emptyset$ As

$$\text{card}(\mathbb{T}_n \cap \mathbb{F}_n) + \text{card}(\mathbb{M}_n) = \text{card}(\mathbb{F}_n)$$

$$\rho(h_n(C_n) \cap \mathbb{F}_n) = \sum_{k=2}^r (-1)^k \sum_{2 \leq i_2 < i_3 \dots < i_k \leq r} \rho\left(\bigcap_{j=2}^k A_{2p_{i_j}+2} \cap \mathbb{F}_n\right)$$

By Chebotarev-Artin theorem we have :

$$\rho\left(\bigcap_{j=2}^k A_{2p_{i_j}+2} \cap \mathbb{F}_n\right) = \frac{\text{card}(\mathbb{F}_n)}{\prod_{j=2}^k (p_{i_j} - 1), p_{i_j} \geq 3} + g(n)$$

and

$$\rho(A_{2p_i+2} \cap \mathbb{F}_n) = \frac{\text{card}(\mathbb{F}_n)}{\phi(2p_i)} - \psi_{p_i+2}, \forall i \geq 2$$

Hence

$$\rho(h_n(C_n) \cap \mathbb{F}_n) = \sum_{k=2}^r (-1)^k \sum_{2 \leq i_2 < i_3 \dots < i_k \leq r} \frac{\text{card}(\mathbb{F}_n)}{\prod_{j=2}^k (p_{i_j} - 1), p_{i_j} \geq 3} - \sum_{k=2}^r \psi_{p_i+2} + g(n)$$

By the USEFULL LEMMA we have :

$$\rho(h_n(C_n) \cap \mathbb{F}_n) = \left[1 - \prod_{i=2}^r \frac{p_i - 2}{p_i - 1}\right] \text{card}(\mathbb{F}_n) - \Pi_2(\sqrt{n}) + g(n)$$

As

$$\text{card}(\mathbb{T}_n \cap \mathbb{F}_n) + \text{card}(\mathbb{M}_n) = \text{card}(\mathbb{F}_n)$$

and

$$\rho(h_n(C_n) \cap \mathbb{F}_n) = \text{card}(\mathbb{T}_n \cap \mathbb{F}_n)$$

then

$$\text{card}(\mathbb{M}_n) = \prod_{3 \leq p \leq \sqrt{n}} \frac{p-2}{p-1} \text{card}(\mathbb{F}_n) + \Pi_2(\sqrt{n}) - g(n)$$

Dividing each term of the previous relation we have

$$\frac{\mathbb{M}_n}{\text{card}(\mathbb{F}_n)} = \prod_{3 \leq p \leq \sqrt{n}} \frac{p-2}{p-1} + P(n)$$

where $P(n) = \frac{\Pi_2(\sqrt{n}) - g(n)}{\text{card}(\mathbb{F}_n)}$.

Moreover $\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} P(n) = 0$ By using Mertens Formula we have

$$\frac{\text{card}(\mathbb{M}_n)}{\text{card}(\mathbb{F}_n)} \sim_{+\infty} \frac{4e^{-\gamma} C_2(n)}{\ln n} \left(1 + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{\ln n}\right)\right)$$

By Theorem 2 we obtain

$$\text{card}(\mathbb{M}_n) \sim_{+\infty} 4e^{-\gamma} \left(2 - \frac{5}{3} C_{artin} - 2K_\infty\right) C_2 \frac{n}{\ln^2 n}$$

Each $p \in \mathbb{M}_n$ is such that $p-6, p-4, p-2$ are all primes.

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